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Study of Mammals of Middle Aravalli and Their Occurrence, Microhabitat Specializations and Ecological Threats

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Abstract

The Mammals are very important part of the vertebrate life. Most mammals are the vital component of the ecosystem as they are present at various levels and tropic organization in good chains and food webs. The current work deals with the evaluation and assessment of total studied mammalian diversity. The study was conducted in the years of 2022, 2023 and 2024-25. the total 30 mammalian species were recorded in the study area of middle Aravalli range and associated areas in the four district namely Ajmer, Beawar, Pali and Rajsamand districts. Mammals were assessed on the grounds of their occurrence, microhabitat specialization and possible threats. Most of them are broadly categorized in Herbivore & Carnivore categories. The most common are Antelopes, Cats, Mongooses, porcupines, monkey, bats, boar, pangolin, Hare, Sloth bear, jackals, Lakkarbaga, sloth bear & panthers. habitat destruction & poaching are major ecological threats.

Keywords Mammals, Microhabitat Specialization, Habitat Destruction, Poaching, Geological Threats, Food Webs and Food Chains.

Introduction

India is a most populated state in the world and constituent a major fraction of world population together with China Despite being most populated country, there are a variety of habitats and ecological niches for different types of plants, animals and wild life. There are Four hot spots of biological diversity in India namely, northern Himalayas, North-eastern India (the hot spot continues with the geographical boundaries of Burma), Sunda land (Which includes the Ganga-Bramaputra Delta and island of Andaman & Nicobar) and very important geohistorical part of western ghats!

The biodiversity of the country, especially status of Indian mammal was estimated and assessed in a CAMP (conservation Assessment and Management plan), organized as a work shop in 1997. The process of CAMP was conducted by a specialist Group of the species and their Survival commission established by IUCN (Seal, 2000). The assessment was done according to the 1994 IUCN Red list Category criteria for evaluation of mammalian taxa of the country.

Rajasthan is the state of India, located in the western boundaries on Radcliffe line between India and Pakistan most of the geographical locality is desert and sand dunes of thar desert, however there are a variety of geographical variations and other habitat types such as Aravalli Hills, Deccan trap (Called Hadoti Plateau in Kota-Bundi-Baran & Jhalawar), North-eastern Plains in Bhratpur - Alwar, Jaipur, Swaimadhopur etc.)

The total population of the state is 8.54 crores in 2025 approximately 6% of the country. The Area of the state is 3,42,239 square Kelo meters which is 10.41% of the total national area. The state was united in 1 Nov 1956 and named as Rajasthan. Politically there are 7 divisions and 41 districts. The state has a wide diversity of Geological and geographical land forms which includes barren hills, forested mountain range of Aravalli, Agriculturally, dominated plain of north-east and Hadoti plateau of fertile soil. The Same diversity is seen in the historical and cultural aspects for example there are thousands of palaces, many historically important forts, stepwells, festivals, fair, religious and cultural occasion, folk

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dances, folk song, folk traditions and important ethnobotanical and ethological things with ethnic diversity.

Although state of Rajasthan Harbors a huge population and do faster it, it simultaneously is a Home for very large and diverse biological community. The floral and faunal components of the state which creator a composite of Biodiversity of the state is also fascinating and very important to nurse different type of plant and Animal species. The diversity of the animals especially the mammals is very important aspect of the state diversity.

The Blackbuck, four-horned antelope, sambar, deer, Chital, northern palm squirrel, Indian leopard, desert jird, sloth bear, otter, fox, pangolin, Nilgai (Blue Bull), wild boar, dromedary camel, River dolphin, Indian Gazella, Jackal, Squirrels field and house rats, Macaque, Langur, Jungle cats, desert cat, small Indian Mongoose, Common field mongoose, shrew, flying fox, short-nosed fruit bats, five striped palm, Squirrel, desert Gerbil, long tailed tree mouse, Kachchh rat, house mouse, Indian bush mouse, Indian mole rat, Indian porcupine, etc. are few examples of the huge mammalian spectrum of the Rajasthan State!

The mammals are though not residing in a particular kind of geographical locality they are being used to wander in a board geographical range according to their size, food need and need of breeding.

But most mammals say small or large their broad geographical range, fidelity (geological fidelity) habitat types, sub habitat and microhabitats with few examples of niche specialization and habitat specialization is a common feature.

The most mammals are classified and can be categorized in their respective nature & being diurnal or nocturnal herbivores or carnivores, predators or prey or a common species in an area or very rare and threatened species according to biodiversity assessments and IUCN Red list categories. The current study of mammals in central Aravalli especially in Ajmer, Pushkar, Rajgarh, Nasirabad-Kishangarh hill range and adjoining sand dunes of Govindgarh-Badighati- Thanwala block & nearest localities of Todgarh- Ravali and Kumbhalgarh WLSs deals with these mammals and the major ecological and geographical area of their occurrence, macro habitat and sub-habitats, microhabitats and Niche specialization in central Aravalli range of Ajmer and Rajsamand-Pali-Nagaur district with Beawar as a Heart land of Historical Ajmer-Merwara state. It also deals with the number of mammalian species and genera occurring in the area. and assessment of threats to these fascinating but endangered collection of Tetrapod.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to study of mammals of middle Aravalli and their occurrence, microhabitat specializations and ecological threats

Review of Literature

Evaluation of mammals of central Aravalli was conducted in the years of 2022, 2023, 2024 and current year of 2025 (Jan to March). Citing and observation was managed in day time, night time, midnight and noon time in different months from January to December in 3 different seasons namely winter, Summer and also in rainy-monsoon season. There are many mammals which falls in different categories of diurnal for example antelopes, gazella, chital, sambhar, deer, Nilgai etc. Nocturnal are wild cats, Jackals, foxes, wild boars fruit bats, cave bats, Indian mole rat, hyenas, Indian porcupine etc.

For identification purpose, checklist was prepared from the checklist of Indian Mammals (Nameer,2000) and also used the Fauna of British India (Pocock, 1939, 41; Blanford 1891,). Nomenclature and Taxonomical treatment of mammalian diversity was done by the help of the Taxonomy and mammals (Wilson and Reeder, 1993) and vertebrates (R.L. Kot pal 2024).

Methodology

(A) Methodology for Primary Data Collection

Mobile camera, Olympus binocular (840) and relevant field guides Taxonomic literature (above mentioned in last para.) were used for proper citing and reference purposes. photography was done by mobile camera & Nikon cameras.

(a) Direct method

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Small mammals were also observed by the transect / quadrat/sample method & estimation of their population parameters was done.

(b) Indirect method:

during the zoological trips & excursions identification was also conducted by indirect methods like, scats, quills, dung pellets and dung piles, identification pugmarks and footprints, and imprinted path ways, tree trunk methodology.

(B) Secondary Data Collection

(a) Villagers/cattle herders Observation based interview and questionnaire methodology because they are familiar and very much experienced in the geographical locality and usual citing places for mammals. Interaction with these guys throughs a flesh back on the story.

(b) Data of wild life experts & forestry wildlife expert views & interviews, forest department report and annual report was also referred.

**Statistics
Used in the
Study**

Topography and Climate of the Study Area

Nagpahar, Taragarh Hills, Badighati, Govindgarh, Mangal Ji ka Mathara, Todgarh Hills, Goram Pahad (Nath Ji ka Magra) Kumbhal Garh, Vero ka Math and Jarga Hills, Haldi Ghati and Unwas Villages are the very important peaks of Aravalli range and associated spots are best places for citing of mammals in Vallys of these Hills & Peaks.

The Aravalli range of Ajmer & Rajsamand, Pali, Beawar districts which are home for 2 important wild life Sanctuaries namely Kumbhalgarh & Todgarh-Raoli Range is Home for mammalian diversity. At the same time the sand dunes & transition zones in western slopes of Aravalli in Beawar district – Near Sandra Village, Desuri, Nadol and Sand dunes Near-Pushkar-Thanwla Badighati are important places for desert mammals.

The Area although is dominated by Aravalli Mountain range also have rocks, clefts, Vallys, Hills, Plateau, Desert dunes, Xeric Habitats, Water bodies, rivers like Banas, Luni, Sagarmati, Saraswati, Khari, Kothari, etc. which foster the plant, animals, society and wild life in the area. The maps of the area shown in fig. on next page

Fig. 01- (a) Map of India with location of Rajasthan (b) Map of Rajasthan with location of Ajmer (c) Map of Aravalli Mountain range nearby of Ajmer

Observations Table

Common name	Zoological name	Occurrence	Microhabitat specialization	Major threats	Conservation status
Bush rat	<i>Golunda ellioti</i>	Shrubby area	Burrowing under bushes	Oran destruction	Least concern
Field mouse	<i>Mus boodunga</i>	Agriculture plains	Crop fields	None	L.C
Small House mouse	<i>Mus musculus</i>	Human settlements	Kitchen/store house burrowing	None	L.C
Forest mongoose	<i>Herpestes smithii</i>	Aravalli Hills	Dense forest patches	Poaching	L.C
Small Indian mongoose	<i>Herpestes javanicus</i>	Agriculture land	Fellow land near crops	Poaching	L.C
Common Indian mongoose	<i>Herpestes edwardsii</i>	Plains/sand dunes	Orans/Fellow land	Habitat loss	L.C
Fruit bats	<i>Pteropus rodricensis</i>	Tree patches	Large Figs/ Fruit trees	Loss of tree cover	Vulnerable
Flying fox	<i>Pteropus giganteus</i>	Rocky Hills/Grooves	Rocky caves/cervices	Loss of Habitat	Least concern
Short nose fruit bats	<i>Cynopterus sphinx</i>	Tree patches/Forest	Forest/Fruit trees	Loss of tree cover	Least concern
Chuchundar	<i>Bandicota bengalensis</i>	Human settlements	Store houses/ware houses	None	L.C
Five stripped palm Squirrel	<i>Funum pennanti</i>	Human settlements/tree patches	Acacia/Neem/ Khejri trees	Loss of trees	L.C
Indian sehi	<i>Hystrix indica</i>	Oran/Forest	Forest/Oran damage/shrub land/Rocks	Habitat loss/Poaching	Vulnerable
Jhau chuha	<i>Paraechinus micropus</i>	Oran	Rocky caves/Shrubbs	Habitat loss/Poaching	Vulnerable
Pangolin	<i>Manis crassicaudata</i>	Rocky forest	Rocky caves	Poaching	Vulnerable
Hare (hulio)	<i>Lepus nigricolis</i>	Oran/Shrub land	Grooves of Euphorbia	Poaching/Habitat loss	Least concern
Gerbil	<i>Tatera indica</i>	Plains	Sand dunes/soil dunes	None	Vulnerable
Lakarbagga(hyena)	<i>Hyaena hyaena</i>	Desert forest land	Forest grooves	Habitat destruction	Vulnerable
Siyar(jackal)	<i>Canis aureus</i>	Rocky orans/Hills	Rock cervices/caves	Mining of Rocks	Near threatened
Desert cat	<i>Felis lybica</i>	Desert area	Sand dunes/Desert grooves	Habitat loss	Vulnerable
Ban Bilav(wild cat)	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	Forest/Orans/Rocks	Oran grooves	Habitat loss	Near threatened
Lynx of desert	<i>Felis caracal</i>	Rocky forest	Rock caves/tree grooves	Habitat destruction	Near threatened
Reechh (sloth bear)	<i>Melursus ursinus</i>	Rocky forest	Rock cervices/Caves	Mining/Habitat loss	Critically Endangered
Monkey	<i>Semnopithecus entellus</i>	Rocky Hills/Forest	Tree trunks/Rocks	Habitat destruction	Least concern
Langur	<i>Macaca mulata</i>	Forest	Tree trunks/Arboreal	Tree loss/deforestation	Least concern
Wild boar	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	Oran/Agricultural fields	Nera Human settlement	Poaching for meat	Least concern
Chinkara	<i>Gazella benettii</i>	Desert land	Sandy grooves	Poaching/Habitat loss	Near threatened
Kala Hiran (black Buck)	<i>Antilope cervicapra</i>	Desert land	Sandy dunes/Tree patches	Poaching/Habitat loss	Near threatened
Chital	<i>Axis axis</i>	Plains/Human settlement	Agricultural fields	Poaching	Not evaluated
Rojda (Nilgai)	<i>Boselaphus tragocamelus</i>	Orans/Human settlement	Agricultural fields	None	Not evaluated
Panther (leopard)	<i>Panthera pardus</i>	Rocky Forest	Tree grooves/Rocks caves	Habitat loss	Vulnerable

Result and Discussion

Total 30 large and small mammals included carnivores and herbivores mostly are nocturnal few are diurnals. Major threats were assessed poaching for meat and body parts like furs, skin, nails and habitat destruction & changing land use pattern are major ecological risks & threats evaluated.

Conclusion

Zoological trips and excursions were conducted in the years of 2022, 2023, 2024 and the current years of the 2025 (up to February).

The mammalian diversity encountered and evaluated in the area includes total 30 species of large and small mammals including carnivores, herbivores. Most of them are very important species of forested areas, few are of rocky terrain and others are found in Rocky orans/Dev vans in the concerned area of study. Nag Pahar, Taragarh Hill- Happy Vally, Ajay pal, Nasirabad-Rajgarh Valley, Govindgarh, Pushkar-Bdighati-Thanwala, Todgarh Hills, Sandra granite park, Todgarh-Dudhaleswar, Jojawar-Bijaji ka Guda,

Nodole, Kumbhal garh, Jarga hills, Goram, Veron ka math are few land mark sites of the study area in middle Aravalli range. Large Herbivores are Nilgai, Sambhar, Kala Hiran, Chinkara, chital, wild boar etc. while small herbivores are five striped squirrel, shrews, rats, mole, hare, Hedge Hog, Porcupines etc. Large carnivores included Predatory and top carnivores like panther (Leopard), Jacka, Lakkarbagga, and Honey bagger.

Small ones are civets, pangolins, and Gerbils, Desert fox, desert cat, wild cat, caracal etc. Arboreal (tree dwellers) included monkeys, Langurs, Flying foxes, squirrels etc. Cave dweller included Panthers, sloth bears, pangolins, Porcupines & Hedge hogs, flying mammal included Flying Foxes, Fruit bats, cave bats and short nose fruit bats.

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